

Rac-4a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-74-1-RAC-10%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	93	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 74 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/29/2021 8:48:30 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/29/2021 9:48:37 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.766	4887755	49.94	259567
2	16.676	4899185	50.06	205730

Asy-4a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-74-2-10%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0729
Vial:	94	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 74 2
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/29/2021 9:14:50 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/29/2021 9:46:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.847	515250	2.52	26189
2	16.657	19951144	97.48	846223